

Effect of global warming on temperature rise due to pollution in the capital city of New Delhi, India in past 25 years

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ABSTRACT

Over the past few decades, air pollution and climate change have become major global concerns. In light of this concern about Indian cities, where air pollution and climate change have a significant health impact, this review was conducted. Human health is at risk from the expanding urban areas that experience extreme climate events like high rainfall, extreme temperature, floods, and droughts. Urban residents are experiencing thermal discomfort and a number of health issues as a result of the elevated temperature levels brought on by the intensified heat waves brought on by climate change. The study also looks at the rising levels of air pollution that are higher than what is required for the majority of Indian megacities. The concentrations of PM and aerosols have been investigated, and the potentially harmful effects on human health of particles that enter the respiratory system and are inhaled by humans have also been discussed. Also looked at were the health effects of the COVID-2019 lockdown on Indian cities' air quality. Lastly, the link between urbanization, air pollution, and climate change has been shown because air pollutants like aerosols affect Earth's climate directly (through absorption and scattering) and indirectly (through modifying cloud properties and radiation transfer processes). As a result, the information in this review will act as a starting point for policymakers when it comes to evaluating vulnerable regions and putting into action plans to reduce air pollution. Based on the review, adaptation and mitigation measures can be implemented in Indian cities to mitigate the effects on human health by regularly monitoring air pollution and addressing climate change.

Key words: Air pollution, environmental threat, health, economic productivity, Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

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INTRODUCTION

According to the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) report released on August 16, 2021, Delhi, India's national capital, may be on its way to becoming the nation's heat capital by the end of this century under the worst emission release scenario. Under the worst-case emission scenario, the capital city's mean temperature could rise by 5.3°C compared to the pre-industrial period by the end of the 21st century. Even in the best emission release scenario, which is expected to limit global average temperature rise to 1.5 degrees Celsius below pre-industrial levels, Delhi's average temperature is expected to rise by at least 2°C. Humanity's only hope of survival is thought to lie at this point. The 2015 Paris Agreement stipulated that the global mean temperature increase should not exceed 1.5 degrees Celsius compared to the pre-industrial temperature benchmark. Under the worst-case scenario for the release of warming emissions, which is primarily caused by high temperatures and severe air

pollution, the rainfall, particularly heavy downpours of short duration, is also expected to rise significantly by the end of the year. According to the analysis, a significant portion of the rise in temperature and rainfall began within the last two decades, highlighting the dramatic increase in recent climate impacts. Experts pointed out that the projection generally follows the trend that has been observed. The highest temperature rise among Indian metros A mean temperature rise of 5.3°C would not only be the highest among all Indian metros, but it would also be higher than Hyderabad, which would likely see an increase of 4.7°C over the same time period. Between 2015 and 2100, nearly 92% of the capital's increase is likely to occur. Under the best possible emission scenario, Representative Concentration Pathway (RCP) 2.6, the mean temperature will rise by 2°C by the end of the century, whereas the moderate RCP 4.5 emission scenario will result in a rise of 2.9°C. The fact that the average maximum temperature may reach 37.4°C is even more troubling; the limit of greatest temperatures is projected to contact 53.7°C if the same old thing discharge go on over the short term. Even if RCP 4.5, the most likely emission scenario that will limit the temperature rise to 2°C, is followed, the maximum temperature is expected to exceed 50°C. According to the analysis, the worst emission scenario would result in temperatures exceeding 35°C for approximately 187 days per year, or about one out of every two days, by the end of the century. We anticipate an RCP 4.5 scenario. KJ Ramesh, a retired director-general of the India Meteorological Department (IMD), stated, "I hope that global leaders will take action to limit the maximum temperature rise to 2°C." Ramesh added that during the height of summer in the capital, the temperature in Delhi can reach nearly 44°C for a few days.

Delhi's temperature reached 43.6°C in July 2020, breaking a 90-year record. The months of February and September in 2020 were the warmest they had been in decades. "The projected temperature rise is generally consistent with the observed trend," says "Projection matches trend." According to climate scientist Roxy Mathew Koll of the Indian Institute of Tropical Meteorology, Pune, "heat waves that are generating in northern India, such as Delhi, Rajasthan, etc., and Pakistan, frequently push the mercury up." India and Pakistan endured one of the hottest and longest heat waves since they began recording weather reports in May and June of 2019. Scientist and lead author of the IPCC report Subimal Ghosh explained that Delhi's heat rise is caused by urbanization, specifically by urban heat islands. Maximum one-day rainfall likely to rise sharply. The analysis also reveals that, depending on the emission scenarios (two degrees Celsius average global warming and later three to four degrees Celsius global warming), the maximum one-day rainfall may rise by nearly 22% and 50% by the century's end. It is anticipated that the trend will experience a significant uptick toward the end of this century. Although the scale is smaller than that of a single day's worth of sudden downpours, total rainfall is also likely to rise. For instance, it is anticipated that total precipitation will only increase by 15% over the next century under the RCP 4.5 scenario.

Even though the IPCC report predicted stronger monsoons and fewer droughts in the coming years, Ghosh stated that the finding was characterized as having "low confidence." Krishnan Raghavan, senior scientist at IITM and coordinating lead author of the IPCC report, stated that, despite the fact that the monsoon's precise nature appeared uncertain in the immediate future (from 2021 to 2040) due to inherent variability, there was some certainty that the monsoon rainfall would increase beyond 2040. However, the report stated that major Indian cities would experience a greater number of bursts of intense rainfall, primarily as a result of urbanization, with "medium confidence." It went on to say that "urbanization intensifies extreme precipitation over the urban area and its down-wind region, especially in the afternoon and early evening." Ghosh noted that the aerosol load that contributes to cloud formation is triggered by the high intensity of heat released in major cities and local air pollution. Delhi, with its combination of extremely high projected heat rise and severe air pollution, is likely to suffer severely from the trend because of its urban structure, which frequently traps the wind and acts together to bring bursts of intense rainfall to Indian cities.

AIR POLLUTION AND CLIMATE CHANGE

Climate change and air pollution are major current threats to rapidly expanding cities. In terms of climate action and sustainable development, developing nations like India, which are transitioning from predominantly rural to increasingly urban settings, must confront significant obstacles (Van Duijne, 2017; C. Singh et al., 2021). By adding 416 million urban dwellers by 2050, it is anticipated that 53% of India's total population will be urban (UNDESA, 2018). The ongoing urbanization of urban areas alters the surface and boundary layer atmospheric properties, thereby influencing regional climate (Shepherd, 2005; Ren and co., 2008; Yang and others, 2012). Additionally, urbanization by altering land

use and land cover has an impact on the climate through increased anthropogenic emissions, extreme precipitation (which may result in urban flooding), higher temperatures, and frequent heat waves with heat-related effects on human health (Chestnut *et al.*, 1998; Ramanathan and others, 2001; Shastri and other, 2015). Different meteorological conditions, such as variations in temperature and precipitation, reflect the shifts in the regional climate. The anthropogenic outflows like ozone depleting substance (GHG) emanations trigger these neighborhood environment changes.

Pollutant emissions and aerosol load in the atmosphere both rise as a result of the growing urban population and vehicular traffic, in addition to the impact of urbanization on the climate. One of the main reasons for the high aerosol loading in the Indian subcontinent is the growing urbanization, population, and industrialization (Kaskaoutis *et al.*, 2011; Ramachandran and others, 2012; Krishna Moorthy and others, 2013). As a result, this study reveals that the interconnectedness of climate change and air pollution is one of the greatest threats to human health and well-being in cities. More than seven million people worldwide die from diseases linked to PM_{2.5} pollution, according to a World Health Organization (WHO) report (WHO, 2015). Due to its rapid development and growing population, India suffers from severe air pollution; According to the WHO Global Urban Ambient Air Pollution Database (Update 2016), nine of the world's ten most polluted cities are located in India. In recent years, a lot of attention has been paid to the rising levels of air pollution in the majority of Indian megacities over the past few decades and the negative effects it has had on human health (such as asthma and cardio-respiratory disease) (Sarath and Ramani, 2014; Gautam and other, 2020; 2020, Shaw and Gorai).

HUMAN HEALTH & CLIMATE CHANGE

Numerous studies have documented the detrimental effects of climate change on human health, and these effects are anticipated to worsen with subsequent climate change (Luber and McGeehin, 2008; Bell and others, 2018; Filippelli and others, 2020). Problems caused by notable extreme weather conditions like rising temperatures, increased precipitation, increased heatwave intensity and frequency, floods, droughts, strong winds, and landslides (Orimoloye *et al.*, 2019). As a result of climate change, extreme heat, extreme cold, and unpredictability in precipitation cause an increase in health problems; as a result of these climatic changes, water- and air-borne infections, vector-borne infections, malnutrition, the prevalence of diarrheal diseases, and heat-related morbidity and mortality have increased (Haines *et al.*, 2006; (2013) (Dutta and Chorsiya). Kids, old individuals, and metropolitan inhabitants are more helpless against these wellbeing influences (Haines *et al.*, 2006; 2010 by Ebi and Paulson; Filippelli and others, 2020). According to Dutta and Chorsiya (2013), climate change has been responsible for approximately 5 million illnesses and 150,000 deaths annually. Some of the human health problems that are directly or indirectly related to climate change include respiratory infections, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, pneumothorax, asthma, allergies, hyperthermia, and dehydration (D'Amato *et al.*, 2011; Filippelli and others, 2020). According to the International Institute for Population Sciences (IIPS) Macro International, approximately 2% of adults and 6% of children in India suffer from respiratory tract infections.

Hence, these super weather patterns have unfavorable wellbeing influences that can likewise bring about loss of lives. Understanding how rising temperatures affect biota is crucial when considering the effects of extreme heat on human health. Skin cancer, heat stroke, heart disease, diarrhea, and an increase in mortality are just a few of the heat-related illnesses that plague cities as a result of climate change (Changnon *et al.*, 1996; 2014, Hondula and Barnett; Orimoloye and others, 2019). According to Dutta and Chorsiya (2013), the effects of heat on human health also include dehydration, heat cramps, heat exhaustion, heat stroke, fluid loss, heat injuries, and eye and skin diseases. A significant effect of climate change is the urban heat island (UHI) effect, or rise in urban temperature. Numerous Indian cities have experienced the UHI effect (Ambinakudige, 2011; Kikon and other, 2016; Matthew and co., 2016; Kaur and Pandey, 2020) making warm inconvenience metropolitan occupants. According to Liu and Zhang (2011), the deterioration of air quality caused by cooling agents is linked to this effect and certain respiratory issues. In addition, Patil and Deepa (2007) report that the heat waves and other frequent weather events in eastern India are significant indicators of climate change. According to Mukherjee and Mishra (2018), the heat waves of 1998 and 2015 each claimed the lives of more than 2000 people in India. Between 1978 and 1999, a heat wave claimed the lives of approximately 1,625 people in Rajasthan, followed by those in Bihar, Uttar Pradesh, and Odisha (De, 2000); While the number of deaths caused by heat rose to 3,442 between 1999 and 2003 (Chaudhury *et al.*, 2000; (2006) Centers for Disease Control and Prevention According to the statistical data presented in a study by Dutta and

Chorsiya (2013), the heat wave that hit India in 2013 resulted in the deaths of more than 600 people. In addition, in the year 2002, the high temperature in Andhra Pradesh (50°C) was responsible for approximately 1,400 deaths. In a similar vein, in 2010, the high temperature in Ahmadabad (46.8°C) claimed the lives of numerous urban residents. In addition, dozens of Indian states, including Rajasthan and Uttarakhand, were significantly affected by the heat waves in 2009 (Dutta and Chorsiya, 2013). Akhtar (2007), Dholakia et al. () reported on the connection between India's heat-related mortality and climate variability. 2015) Murari K. K. et al. for Ahmedabad (Mazdiyasi et al. (2015) 2017). Additionally, an increase in heat-related mortality of fourfold by 2050 and twelvefold by 2,100 has been predicted as a result of the increasing frequency of hot days and nights from 1951 to 2016 (Mukherjee and Mishra, 2018; C. Singh et al., 2021).

Drought, floods, tsunamis, cyclones, and other extreme events that have a negative impact on human health have all been linked to climate change. Metropolitan dry spell and floods made by changing environment due shortage or abundance of precipitation in a roundabout way influences human wellbeing. Floods have physical effects on human health, including trauma, hypothermia, and drowning (Ahern et al., 2005; Du and co., 2010). According to Dutta and Chorsiya (2013), severe drought conditions that resulted in a lack of food caused a significant number of deaths due to starvation in India. In addition, the heavy rains that cause floods result in the destruction of crops, which in turn results in a lack of food, which in turn causes malnutrition and problems with public health. According to the World Bank Report on Malnutrition in India (2009), nearly 47% of children in India are at risk for malnutrition. In India, about 70% of children, 55% of women, and 25% of men suffer from anemia as a result of malnutrition (Majra and Gur, 2009). According to Dutta and Chorsiya (2013), climate change's rise in sea level could result in fatal flooding. Additionally, the availability of fresh water decreases as a result of the drought and flood conditions. According to Mondal et al., an increase in the risk of diarrheal diseases caused by floods has been reported for India. 2001). Waterborne infections like *E. coli*, cholera, typhoid, cryptosporidium, shigella, giardia, and viruses like hepatitis A can spread through the contaminated water (Gabastou et al., 2002; 2008, Kovats and Akhtar; Gur and Majra, 2009). Additionally, certain rodent-borne diseases like tularemia, leptospirosis, and viral hemorrhagic diseases are brought on by floods. Other diseases associated with Baltimore and London's climate variability include Lyme disease, Hantavirus pulmonary syndrome, and tick-borne encephalitis (Wilson et al., 2001; Gur and Majra, 2009). In addition, extreme weather events caused by climate change, such as cyclones, tsunamis, and floods, have displaced millions of people and killed thousands in numerous Indian states, including Assam, Bihar, West Bengal, Odisha, Uttar Pradesh, Himachal Pradesh, Rajasthan, and Gujarat (World Health Organization, 2005). Gur and Majra, 2009). These occasions additionally cause antagonistic wellbeing influences on enduring populace. These extreme weather events, which have been reported in recent years, include:

In 1998 and 2004, Odisha experienced a heat wave; in 2003, Andhra Pradesh experienced a heat wave; in 2004, Uttar Pradesh and Uttaranchal experienced a cold wave; in 2004, Tsunami struck Tamil Nadu, Andhra Pradesh, Kerala, and the Andaman-Nicobar Islands; in 2005, Mumbai, India's largest city, received the most precipitation; in 2005, Andhra Pradesh experienced a cyclone; in 2005, Gujarat and Madhya Pradesh. The transmission of infectious vectors like plague, Japanese encephalitis, malaria, dengue fever, chikungunya, and filariasis increases as a result of these disasters (Bhattacharya et al., 2006; 2006, Devi and Jauhari; Dhiman and other, 2008; Bush and co., 2011). In addition, these disasters have had a devastating impact on states in India, including Surat, Odisha, West Bengal, Jharkhand, Chattisgarh, Madhya Pradesh, and the North East (Kumar et al., 2007). According to Dutta and Chorsiya (2013), the coastal regions of India are susceptible to cyclones and tsunamis. Water-borne diseases like amoebiasis, cryptosporidiosis, giardiasis, typhoid, and cholera are also brought on by these disasters. According to the World Health Organization (WHO) and the United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF), 900,000 Indians die annually from inhaling polluted air and drinking contaminated water. Additionally, the Indian Ministry of Health estimates that 1.5 million children between the ages of 0 and 5 die annually. Diarrhea kills between 0.6 and 0.7 million children under 5 every year in India.

PARTICULATE MATTER AND AEROSOLS

Aerosols have been identified as one of the main air pollutants that have a significant impact on air quality and public health (Xu et al., 2014). Several studies have used either ground-based observations or satellite data to monitor the concentration of aerosols in the atmosphere to determine aerosol optical depth (AOD), an optical property. Because these values are closely linked with air pollutants like

PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, NO₂, SO₂, and O₃, the AOD values are extensively used to represent the level of air pollution, reflect atmospheric conditions, and define climatic effects (Chu et al., 2003; Xu and co., 2014; Li and other, 2016; Awais and other, 2018; Ahmad and co., 2020). As India has been recognized as one of the regional hot spots for aerosols as a result of increasing anthropogenic activities in the country, the monitoring of aerosols has been carried out in a number of Indian cities. Poor air quality reduces visibility as a result of the high aerosol load in the atmosphere, which has negative effects on human health (Davidson et al., 2005). According to Chowdhury and Dey (2016), the exposure to particulate matter, particularly PM_{2.5}, or particles with a diameter of less than 2.5 millimeters, has been identified as the fifth leading risk factor worldwide and the third leading risk factor in India, resulting in approximately 1 million premature deaths annually. Collaborators for the GBD 2015 Risk Factors, 2016; Conibear and others, 2018; Chen and others, 2020). The PM_{2.5} can enter profound into the human body and consequently can cause more serious gamble among any remaining air poisons (Xing et al., 2016). Dust, emissions from biomass burning, emissions from burning open waste, and emissions from the household and power sector are major sources of high PM_{2.5} concentrations in India (Guo et al., 2017; Conibear and others, 2018; Venkataraman and others, 2018). Major urban sources of PM_{2.5} include domestic heating and cooking, dust from construction, and industrial emissions (Guttikunda et al., 2019). Rajput and others 2014) reported that during paddy residue burning in the Patiala region of Punjab in October and November, PM_{2.5} mass concentrations ranged from 60 to 390 gm³, with a significant contribution from organic carbon (OC); Nevertheless, the mass concentration of PM_{2.5} ranges from 18 to 123 gm³ during the April-May wheat residue burning period.

In addition, emissions from the rural areas surrounding the city also contribute to India's urban pollution (Guttikunda et al., 2019; Ravindra and other, 2019), non-local sources (agricultural crop burning in the neighboring states) contribute more than 30% in Delhi, while local sources (such as traffic, power plants, and industries) account for less than 70% of total PM_{2.5} (Guo et al., 2017; Prabhakaran and others, 2020). In addition, the addition of additional pollutants to the situation is made worse by the burning of fireworks during the Diwali festival in Delhi (Ganguly et al., 2019). PM_{2.5} pollution is anticipated to continue rising in the coming decades as a result of urbanization (Chowdhury et al., 2018; Conibear and others, 2018).

CONCLUSION

The present investigation reveals that the majority of Indian megacities experience high levels of air pollution, with pollutant concentrations that are above the acceptable threshold. The necessity of continuous monitoring of air pollutants over the Indian subcontinent using measurements and remote sensing satellite data is highlighted by the continuous emissions from both anthropogenic and natural sources that result in high PM concentrations and adverse effects on human health. By analyzing vulnerable areas, this review's essential information on air pollutant levels in various Indian megacities can assist in the development of efficient mitigation strategies for each city. The data can make it easier to create a baseline for air quality modeling studies that can accurately predict levels of air pollution for plans that effectively prepare for, adapt to, and mitigate air pollution. To effectively control the concentration of air pollutants across the nation, it is important to emphasize the high mortality and disease burden caused by air pollution in Indian cities. In addition, the findings that showed a decrease in air pollution during the COVID-19 lockdown period suggest that such brief restrictions on pollution mitigation be implemented in various Indian cities to improve air quality and, as a result, human health. In addition, the review points out that climate change is having a negative impact on human health in India, a developing nation. With rising temperatures brought on by climate change, Indian cities are vulnerable to extreme weather events like high precipitation, floods, droughts, and heat waves. In the near future, severe impacts on human health in Indian cities may be mitigated with the assistance of an increase in health surveillance for heat waves, floods, and diseases transmitted by vectors caused by climate change. Additionally, the high population density and ongoing urbanization and industrialization in India must be taken into account in order to avoid adverse health effects from climate change. Therefore, essential strategies for mitigation and adaptation are required to avoid the numerous adverse effects on human health that will result from climate change in Indian cities. These effects, both current and anticipated, are discussed in the review.

In conclusion, monitoring and mapping the spatial-temporal distribution patterns of air pollution, climate change, and the health effects that come with them can greatly benefit from the utilization of

cutting-edge technologies like satellite data and geospatial techniques. Therefore, in order to avoid adverse effects on health, proper urban planning and sustainable measures should be taken for sustainable urban environments while the focus is on building smart cities in developing nations like India.

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